

Reward System Management and Employees Productivity in Hospitality Industry in Lagos State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Employee productivity is a variable that has been researched over time. However, researchers have not agreed upon factors that really influence the variable. This study investigated the effect of a reward management system on employee productivity in the hospitality industry in Lagos State, Nigeria. The population consisted of all the staff members of one hundred and three (103) hotels registered under booking.com as hotels in Lagos State. The Yamane formula was used at 0.05 level of significance to arrive at a sample size of 82 hotels. The study used purposive sampling, considering the availability of the respondents to select by cadre (stratum), four respondents per hotel, resulting in 328 employees. The research instrument used was a questionnaire. Data were analysed using descriptive and regression statistics tools. The results showed that Reward System ($\beta = .106$, $t = 2.843$, $P < .05$), ($r = 0.685$) has a relative influence and significant relationship with employee productivity. The study also showed that one of the characteristics of the hospitality industry in the study area is the competitive salary paid to workers and timely promotion enjoyed by the staff members. At the same time, the most popular and highly favoured forms of reward system constituted of salary and bonus packages. The study concluded that reward management practices enhanced the productivity of employees. The study recommended that entrepreneurial organisations should make reward management systems essential for improved employee productivity/performance.

Keywords: Employee Performance, Reward System, Incentives, Health Benefits, Salary

Introduction

Productivity in any form is critical to an organisation's overall performance in meeting its objectives, mission, and vision. Managing resources effectively and efficiently to ensure the quality of output for better performance is referred to as organisational Productivity (Okafor, 2019 and Armstrong, 2019). Research has been done worldwide over the years to identify the factors that influence productivity. Findings indicated that productivity is affected by relatively few factors, some of which are organisational-specific, while others can be considered universal. In general, most businesses and their

managers face the challenges of identifying those variables that contribute most to employees' productivity, especially in the effective and efficient utilisation of resources to achieve the Organisation's goals and objectives..

However, there are several perspectives on the term "productivity." Many professionals from various disciplines have considered productivity as a ratio of output to input. Accountants and Financial analysts emphasise that productivity reflects financial performance in terms of return on investment, profitability, growth, turnover, turnover rate, cash inflow, and other factors. Many researchers believe that productivity includes quality and quantity of output (Phina, Arinze and Chukwuma, 2017). Some researchers (Okafor, 2019 and Daniel, 2019) have defined productivity as an organisation's output per person-hour, intended to improve the operation's efficiency and effectiveness. No wonder some productivity-related studies have observed that absenteeism rates impact employees' productivity (Awan, Habib, Shoaib and Naveed, 2020 and Aktaruzzaman and Rahim, 2021).

Generally speaking, productivity refers to two essential characteristics. First, productivity is closely related to resource utilisation and availability. Second, productivity is inextricably linked to value creation, while value creation in any organisation is a product of a performance management system, including the reward management system (Owino, Oluoch and Kimemia, 2019). Thus, high productivity is achieved when the activities and resources used in the manufacturing sector add value to the goods produced. The proper use of resources and the creation of values that represent the core of productivity in an organisation underpin the foundation of an organisation's reward management system. To that extent, it is believed that there is a strong relationship between Reward Management System and Organisational Productivity (Okeke, Onyekwelu, Akpua and Dunkwu, 2019 and Berry, 2003). The term "reward system" refers to the available employers' tools that are used to attract, retain, stimulate, and gratify employees (Okeke, Onyekwelu, Akpua and Dunkwu, 2019). A reward is an expression of gratitude that may be monetary or otherwise extended to employees for their additional output (Okeke, Onyekwelu, Akpua and Dunkwu, 2019; Were and Nyakwara, 2018; Elliot, 2019; Ouma and Karanja, 2018; Backlund and Suikki, 2015; Hirt, 2011; Martyn, 2012 and Coole, 2005). To achieve this, top management must define each employee's job clearly and appropriately.

The evolution of reward management, according to Blau (2009), may be divided into three categories, namely, coercive (work harder or lose your job), remunerative (work harder and get paid more), and normative (work harder and be rewarded or work harder to achieve organisational goals). These findings provided a severe challenge to those who assume that reward outcomes and appraisal outcomes must be tightly separated. This implies that when good performance is recognised and rewarded, the possibility of it happening again is increased. In contrast, poor performance is discouraged or even penalised to lower the likelihood of it happening again. Verbal rewards boost task interest and performance; physical rewards boost motivation when provided to people for completing

tasks or reaching or exceeding preset performance standards (Berry, 2003). Studies have shown that in the public sector, appraisals were widely used to recognise or reward employees for a well-done job. On the whole, studies have shown that every organisation, normally, have one or more of the following reward systems: incentives, appreciation, health benefits, bonuses or salary (Okafor, 2019).

Elliot (2019) opined that salary as a reward scheme, was the primary mechanism utilised by the corporation to reward its employees. Still, little is known about how it works in the rewards system. Coole (2005) opined that to understand how salary affects performance, the organisation must understand the employees' preferences before arriving at a meaningful compensation structure. Likewise, Chebet (2015) stated that managers find it challenging to deal with the pay issue and to link the performance with financial incentive because the strategies to do so are not very clear.

Employee productivity and monetary rewards such as salary pay and bonus remuneration, according to Blau (2009) and Phina, Arinze, and Chukwuma (2017), have a strong positive correlation because the reward system has provision for bonus on top of the employee's basic salary or hourly pay. The purpose of this bonus scheme is to boost staff productivity and performance (Berry, 2003; Okafor, 2017; Blau 2009; Elliot, 2019; Okafor, 2019; and Daniel, 2019). However, Okafor (2019) claimed that there is limited research investigating the relationship between productivity and reward systems in most industrial companies. It may be argued that most employees and employers seem unaware of what constitutes productivity indicators despite their strategic importance and the extent to which these productivity indicators/parameters contribute to work performance (Armstrong, 2019). There is scant evidence that examined the effectiveness of the pay package on the productivity of workers in the Hospitality industry in Lagos state, Nigeria. Equally worrisome is the lack of openness in the reward system, appraisal and poor feedback mechanism in evaluating employees' productivity/performance (Berry, 2003). Thus, one can easily conclude that in the current dwindling Nigerian economy, the reward management system in a given company might be ineffective; and can adversely affect employee productivity/performance, leading to dwindling morale among industrial workers. Hence, exploring the ways of implementing a highly effective and successful reward management system in the hospitality industry in Nigeria is quite timely and has become the overall aim of this research. In a developing nation like Nigeria, observation has shown that the performance management cycle in many firms has been reduced to a transient activity at the end of the financial year, which fails to reflect how employees have performed over one year. This raises the question of whether performance management programs with an emphasis on reward management systems have an impact on workers' efficiency. Against this background, the researcher wants to determine the influence of reward management systems on employee productivity in the hospitality industry in Lagos State, Nigeria. It is expected that contributions to knowledge in this study will focus on the observed phenomena regarding whether there is a significant relationship between productivity and reward systems in Hospitality Industry.

Consequently, the study aimed at assessing the reward management system and employee productivity in the hospitality Industry in Lagos State, Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives of this study are to:

- I. explore reward system characteristics in hospitality industry in Lagos state, Nigeria
- ii. determine the staff's opinion on the elements of employees' productivity
- iii. investigate the most preferred reward system used in hospitality industry in Lagos state, Nigeria
- iv. examine the extent to which reward systems for employees lead to effective employees productivity in the selected hospitality industry in Lagos State and
- v. recommend preferred solutions for enhancing employees' productivity in future.

Lastly, the study tested the hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the reward management system and employee productivity in the hospitality industry, Lagos state, Nigeria.

The population of this study represented all the staff members of one hundred and three (103) hotels registered under booking.com as hotels in Lagos state. The Yamane formula was used at 0.05 significance level to arrive at 82 hotels for this study. The study used purposive sampling, considering the availability of the respondents to select by cadre (stratum), four respondents per hotel resulting in the selection of 328 employees. The research instruments used for data collection were in-depth interviews and questionnaires.

Result and Discussion

Table 1 presented the descriptive analysis of the demography of the respondents in the study. From the table, it was seen that 30% of the respondents to the survey were males, while females were 70%. This implies that, more females were found to be working in the selected hotels. This finding was probably like that because in Nigeria, females are more caring, especially to the visitors than male counterparts. The marital status of the respondents showed that single workers were 70%, married ones were 20.2% and divorcees were 9.8%. Furthermore, from the table 1, based on educational qualification, 40.8% of the respondents have OND and NCE, 49.3% have BSC and HND while 9.9% have MSc and MBA. The implication here was that there were more respondents that were single because hotels in Lagos have been observed to be known to be places where sex activities normally take place and therefore many Nigerian husbands would not ordinarily allow their spouses to work in such environments. Also, it was found that there were more respondents with OND and NCE working in the hotels, showing that the hotels' management probably preferred workers with OND/NCE to university degrees. In depth interview with managers revealed that this was because minimum wages payable by law to OND/NCE certificate holders were smaller than degree holders and also because OND/NCE holders educational training were more practical than degrees' holders whose education were believed to be theoretical .

The table 1 further revealed that 80.3% of the respondents have been in the job for less than 5 years. 9.9% have worked for 5-10 years, and 9.9% have worked above 10 years in hotels. This showed that the hotel management preferred younger generation to work in the hotels because, according to the in depth interview, they were more caring and respectful than the elderly ones. By the Nigerian culture, especially among the native Yorubas, its easier and more comfortable for the visitors to be entertained by young workers than the elderly ones.

Table 1 Breakdown of Demographic Data of the Respondents

Demographic Information		F	%
Gender	Male	64	30.0
	Female	149	70.0
Marital status	Single	149	70.0
	Married	43	20.2
	Divorced	21	9.8
Educational Qualification	Ond/nce	87	40.8
	Bsc/HND	105	49.3
	Msc/MBA	21	9.9
Experience on the Job	Less than 5 yrs	171	80.3
	5-10 yrs	21	9.9%
	Above 10 yrs	21	9.9%

Source: Field Survey. 2022

Reward System Characteristics in Hotels

Table 2 showed the descriptive analysis of respondents' opinions on the characteristics of the reward system in the study area. The table 2 showed that 36.2% of the respondents strongly agreed that there was an adequate pay package in the hotel, 31% agreed to that, 9.9% partially agreed, 7.5% disagreed, and 7.5% strongly disagreed. Again, the table 2 showed that 41.3% strongly agreed that fringe benefits were in place for all employees in the hotel. An in-depth interview with all the senior managers in the targeted hotels revealed that the fringe benefits encompassed incentives, appreciation, health benefits, bonuses and other salary packages that varied from one hotel to another depending on whether it was a one-star hotel, 2-star, 3-star, 4-star or 5-star hotels. The in-depth interview showed that salary and bonus packages were the most prominent and highly favoured in the reward system in the study area. The mean and standard deviation values showed that, on average, the respondents agreed that there was an adequate pay package in the hotel where they work. Furthermore, from the table 2, it was seen that 40.4% of the respondents strongly agreed that employees were recognised for the jobs that they were doing in the hotel.

Table 2: Descriptive Analysis of Reward System

Reward System	SA	A	PA	PD	D	SD	Mean	Total Standard Deviation
	F	F	F	F	F	F		
	%	%	%	%	%	%		
There is an adequate pay package in this hotel	77 36.2%	66 31.0%	21 9.9%	16 7.5%	17 8.0%	16 7.5%	4.57	1.58
Employees are recognised for jobs done in the hotel	86 40.4%	52 24.4%	21 9.9%	23 10.8%	15 7.0%	16 7.5%	4.58	1.61
There are fringe benefits in place for employees in this hotel	88 41.3%	50 23.5%	26 12.2%	17 8.0%	17 8.0%	15 7.0%	4.61	1.60
The salary in this hotel is comparable to what is paid in other hotels	76 36.4%	62 29.7%	17 8.1%	22 10.5%	17 8.1%	15 7.2%	4.54	1.60
Employees are not delayed when it is time for a promotion	90 42.3%	33 15.5%	22 10.3%	37 17.4%	15 7.0%	16 7.5%	4.46	1.67

Source: Field Survey, (2022)

This assertion was supported by 24.4% of the respondents agreeing to the statement and 9.9% partially agreeing. It was also shown that 10.8% of the respondents partially disagreed with the statement, with 7% and 7.5% supporting by disagreeing and strongly disagreeing, respectively. On average, the respondents agreed that employees were recognised for the jobs that they were doing in the hotel.

In an attempt to gauge the productivity capability of the targeted hotels in the study area, respondents were requested to offer their opinions on the feedback performance in their working places. Table 3 showed the interpretation of the descriptive analysis of the performance feedback.

Table 3: Descriptive Analysis of Performance Feedback

Performance Feedback	SA	A	PA	PD	D	SD	Mean	Total Standard Deviation
	F	F	F	F	F	F		
	%	%	%	%	%	%		
There is adequate feedback on my performance.	66 31.0%	59 27.7%	43 20.2%	17 8.0%	15 7.0%	13 6.1%	4.49	1.48
The work activities in this hotel provide direct and clear information about the effectiveness	67 31.5%	71 33.3%	22 10.3%	22 10.3%	16 7.5%	15 7.0%	4.50	1.55
My supervisor provides me with information about my performance in this hotel	48 22.5%	71 33.3%	27 12.7%	17 8.0%	34 16.0%	16 7.5%	4.16	1.62
My weaknesses are revealed from my performance in this hotel	48 22.5%	94 44.1%	0 0.0%	39 18.3%	32 15.0%	0 0.0%	4.41	1.40
There is room for improvement on this job	48 22.5%	81 38.0%	38 17.8%	16 7.5%	15 7.0%	15 7.0%	4.40	1.46

Source: Field Survey, (2022).

The respondents believed that there was adequate feedback on their performance, where 31.0% strongly agreed, 27.7% agreed, and 20.2% partially agreed, while 8.0% partially disagreed and 7.0% disagreed, with 6.1% strongly disagreed. A mean of 4.49 affirmed that the respondents strongly agreed that there was adequate feedback on their performance. When asked if the work activities in hotel provide direct and clear information for their effectiveness on the job, 31.5% had a strongly agreed opinion, 33.3% agreed, and 10.3% partially, while 10.3% also partially disagreed, 7.5% disagreed, with 7.5% strongly disagreed. A mean of 4.50 showed that the respondents agreed that the work activities in hotel provided direct and clear information about their effectiveness on the job and at their work posts. Responses to the following statement in the questionnaire- "My supervisor provide me with information about my performance in this hotel' showed that 22.5% strongly agreed, 33.3% agreed, 12.7% partially agreed, and 8.0% partially disagreed. In comparison, 16.0% disagreed and 7.5% strongly disagreed. A mean of 4.16 and standard deviation of 1.62 indicated that the respondents tended to agree that supervisors provided them with information about their performances in the hotel.

Furthermore, 22.5% strongly agreed that their weaknesses were revealed from their performances in the hotel, with 44.1% agreed, while 18.3% partially disagreed and 15.0% disagreed, with a mean score of 4.41 and a standard deviation of 1.40. This showed that respondents agreed that their weaknesses were revealed from their performances in the hotel. Lastly, respondents' opinions on whether there was room for improvement on their job varied; 22.5% strongly agreed, 38.0% agreed, and 17.8% partially agreed, while 7.5% partially disagreed, 7.0% disagreed with a mean score of 4.40 and standard deviation of 1.46. This showed that, on average, the respondents agreed that their job had room for improvement.

Also, to gauge the productivity capability of the targeted workers in the study area, respondents were requested to offer their opinions on the employees' performances at their working places. Their responses were presented in table 4 which showed that 40.4% of the respondents strongly agreed that there was an opportunity for employee participation, while 26.8% agreed. Differing opinion showed that 8.0% of the respondents partially disagreed that there was an opportunity for employee participation, 17.8% disagreed, and 7.0% strongly disagreed. The mean value of 4.43 and standard deviation of 1.77 showed that the respondents strongly agreed that there was an opportunity for employee participation. The table also showed that 22.1% of the respondents strongly agreed that workers were allowed to use their initiatives with 29.1% agreed while 15.0% partially agreed. Opposing responses showed that 8.0% partially disagreed and 8.0% strongly disagreed, while 17.8% of the respondents disagreed that workers were allowed to use their initiatives. The mean value of 4.06 and standard deviation of 1.64 showed that on average, the respondents agreed that workers were allowed to use their initiatives. Furthermore, 41.3% of the respondents strongly agreed that workers were allowed to serve as checks on each other's performances. The divergent opinions showed that 7.5% partially disagreed that workers were allowed to serve as checks on each other's performance, 17.8% disagreed

and 8.0% strongly disagreed. The mean value of 4.31 and standard deviation of 1.80 showed that on the average, the respondents strongly agreed that workers were allowed to serve as checks on each other's performance. Additionally, the table 3 revealed that 30.5% of the respondents strongly agreed that workers tried to avoid absenteeism, 16.4% agreed, and 20.7% partially agreed. Contrarily, 9.9% of the respondents partially disagreed, 15.5% disagreed and 7.0% strongly disagreed. With a mean value of 4.15 and a standard deviation of 1.65, the respondents, on average strongly agreed that workers try to avoid absenteeism. Finally, the table revealed that 29.6% of the respondents strongly agreed that their customers were satisfied with services rendered by workers; 34.7% agreed, and 10.3% partially agreed. Differing views on the responses showed that 9.9% of the respondents partially disagreed that customers were satisfied with services rendered by workers, 8.0% disagreed and 7.5% strongly disagreed. The mean value of 4.46 and standard deviation of 1.56 revealed that on average, the respondents agreed that customers were satisfied with services rendered by the workers.

Table 4. Descriptive Analysis of Employee Performance Appraisal

Employee Performance Appraisal	SA	A	PA	PD	D	SD	Total	
	F	F	F	F	F	F	Mean	Standard Deviation
	%	%	%	%	%	%		
There is an opportunity for employee participation	86 40.4%	57 26.8%	0 0.0%	17 8.0%	38 17.8%	15 7.0%	4.43	1.77
Workers are allowed to use their initiatives	47 22.1%	62 29.1%	32 15.0%	17 8.0%	38 17.8%	17 8.0%	4.06	1.64
Workers are allowed to serve as checks on each other's performance.	88 41.3%	32 15.0%	22 10.3%	16 7.5%	38 17.8%	17 8.0%	4.31	1.80
Workers try to avoid absenteeism	65 30.5%	35 16.4%	44 20.7%	21 9.9%	33 15.5%	15 7.0%	4.15	1.65
Our customers are satisfied with services rendered by our workers	63 29.6%	74 34.7%	22 10.3%	21 9.9%	17 8.0%	16 7.5%	4.46	1.56

Source: Field Survey, (2022)

Table 5 showed the descriptive analysis of respondents (Management) on employee productivity. Here, it could be seen that 31.9% of the respondents strongly agreed that the work quality of employees improved because of the motivation derived from the reward system, 34.7% agreed, 9.9% of respondents partially agreed, 7.5% partially disagreed, while 8.0% disagreed and 8.0% strongly disagreed with mean = 4.51 and standard deviation = 1.58; meaning that, on the average the respondents (Managers) agreed that the work quality of employees improved due to the motivation derived from the

reward system. Furthermore, 23.5% of the respondents strongly agreed that workers completed tasks with speed while 31.5% agreed and 19.7% partially agreed. Other opinions showed that 9.9% partially disagreed, while 8.0% disagreed and 7.5% strongly disagreed with a mean of 4.28 and standard deviation of 1.52. Table 5 revealed further that 23.0% of the respondents strongly agreed that workers discharged their duties efficiently while 31.5% agreed and 19.7% partially agreed; with 9.9% partially disagreed, 8.0% disagreed and 8.0% strongly disagreed. The mean value of 4.28 and standard deviation of 1.52 showed that in overall; the respondents agreed that workers discharged their duties efficiently.

Additionally, 23.9% of the respondents strongly agreed that workers gave attention to priority tasks in the hotels while 31.9% of the respondents agreed and 19.7% partially disagreed. On the contrary, 9.9% of the respondents partially disagreed, and another 7.5% disagreed and 7.0% strongly disagreed. A mean value of 4.34 and a standard deviation of 1.49 revealed that respondents agreed that workers gave attention to prioritising tasks in the hotel. Also, table 5 showed that 13.1% of the respondents strongly agreed that workers put in necessary work effort while 54.0% agreed, 7.5% partially agreed. Contrary opinions revealed that 10.3% of the respondents partially disagreed that workers put in necessary efforts to accomplish their tasks on the job, 8.0% disagreed and 7.0% strongly disagreed. The mean value of 4.33 and SD of 1.42 showed that the respondents agreed our workers put in the necessary commitment on the job. Table 5 revealed that 20.7% of the respondents strongly agreed that customers were given maximum attention and care with 46.9% agreed and 9.9% partially agreed. Other opinions revealed that 7.5% of the respondents partially disagreed, 7.5% disagreed and 7.5% strongly disagreed. The mean value of 4.43 and standard deviation of 1.47 showed that the respondents agreed that customers were given maximum attention and care. Furthermore, 24.9% of the respondents strongly agreed that workers spent less time to achieve reliable results, 30.0% agreed while 19.7% partially agreed. On the contrary, 9.9% of the respondents partially disagreed with 8.0% disagreed and 7.5% strongly disagreed.

Table 5: Descriptive Analysis of Employee Productivity based on Managers’ opinions

Employee Productivity	SA	A	PA	PD	D	SD	Total	
	F %	F %	F %	F %	F %	F %	Mean	Standard Deviation
The work quality of our employees has improved	68 31.9%	74 34.7%	21 9.9%	16 7.5%	17 8.0%	17 8.0%	4.51	1.58
Our workers complete tasks with speed	50 23.5%	67 31.5%	42 19.7%	21 9.9%	17 8.0%	16 7.5%	4.30	1.51
Our workers discharge their duties efficiently	49 23.0%	67 31.5%	42 19.7%	21 9.9%	17 8.0%	17 8.0%	4.28	1.52
Our workers give attention to priority tasks in this hotel	51 23.9%	68 31.9%	42 19.7%	21 9.9%	16 7.5%	15 7.0%	4.34	1.49
Our workers put in the necessary time on the job in this hotel	28 13.1%	115 54.0%	16 7.5%	22 10.3%	17 8.0%	15 7.0%	4.33	1.42
Our customers are given maximum attention and care	44 20.7%	100 46.9%	21 9.9%	16 7.5%	16 7.5%	16 7.5%	4.43	1.47
Our workers spend less time to achieve reliable results	53 24.9%	64 30.0%	42 19.7%	21 9.9%	17 8.0%	16 7.5%	4.31	1.52
Our customers provide positive feedbacks on the actions of our workers	49 23.0%	68 31.9%	20 9.4%	38 17.8%	21 9.9%	17 8.0%	4.16	1.59
Our workers are good at time management	74 34.7%	62 29.1%	22 10.3%	19 8.9%	20 9.4%	16 7.5%	4.48	1.61
Our workers have shown great consistency on the job	72 33.8%	46 21.6%	16 7.5%	42 19.7%	21 9.9%	16 7.5%	4.27	1.67

Source: Field Survey, 2022.

With a mean of 4.31 and a standard deviation of 1.52, the respondents agreed that workers spent less time achieving reliable results. Also, the table 5 revealed that 23.0% of the respondents strongly agreed that customers provide positive feedback on the actions of workers, 31.9% agreed and 9.4% partially agreed. The contrary views showed that 17.8% of the respondents partially disagreed while 9.9% disagreed and 8.0 strongly disagreed. The mean value of 4.16 and standard deviation of 1.59 implied that, on average, the respondents agreed that customers provided positive feedback on the actions of workers. Additionally, the table 5 revealed that 34.7% of the respondents strongly agreed that their workers were good at time management, 29.1% agreed, and 10.3% partially agreed. Contrarily, 8.9% of the respondents partially disagreed, 9.4% disagreed and 7.5% strongly disagreed. With a mean value of 4.48 and a standard deviation of 1.61, the respondents strongly agreed that workers were good at time management. Finally, the table 5 revealed that 33.8% of the respondents strongly agreed that workers had shown great consistency on the job, 21.6% agreed, and 7.5% partially agreed. Differing views on the responses showed that 19.7% of the respondents partially disagreed that workers had shown great consistency on the job, 9.9% disagreed and 7.5% strongly disagreed. The mean value of 4.27 and standard deviation of 1.67 revealed that, on average, the respondents agreed that workers had shown great consistency on the job.

The study tested the hypothesis that there will be no significant relationship between the performance management system (reward system) and employee productivity in the hospitality

industry in Lagos state, Nigeria. Table 6 showed the Pearson product-moment correlation result of the test of the relationship between the reward system and employee productivity. The table 6 revealed that the R value = 0.685. This implied that a 68.5% correlation existed between the reward system and employee productivity. The p-value of the analysis was seen to be 0.000, which was less than 0.05 alphas. With this, the analysis is statistically significant. The implication here is that there is a significant relationship between the reward system and employee productivity.

Table 6: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Result between Reward System and Employee Productivity.

		Reward System	Employee Productivity
Reward System	Pearson Correlation	1	.685**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	213	213
Employee Productivity	Pearson Correlation	.685**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	213	213

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Survey, (2022).

Discussion of Findings

In line with the objective one, the findings confirmed that one of the characteristics of the reward system in the hospitality industry in Lagos state, Nigeria is the adequacy of the pay package. The majority of the respondents, about 77% gave positive responses to confirm this assertion in table 2, comprising of 36.2% strongly agreed (SA), 31% (Agreed) and 10% partially agreed (PA). Another characteristic is that good employees were normally recognised by the management and rewarded with bonuses in addition to their normal salary package. The majority, about 74% gave positive responses to affirm this assertion in table 2, comprising of 40.4% (SA), 24% (Agreed) and 10% (PA); while the majority, about 77% comprising of 41.3% (SA), 23.5% (Agreed) and 12.2% (PA) affirmed that the hospitality industry had adequate fringe benefits for all employees in the study area. Another characteristic of the reward system in the hospitality industry as shown in table 2 is that the reward system is prioritised (comparable to other hotels) as majority of about 74% were positive to this assertion with 36.4% (SA), 29.7% (Agreed) and 8.1% (PA). This implied that all the hotels have a harmonised reward system, and there was a flow of communication among all the hotels' management. This finding reduced labour turnover and the mobility of workers in the hospitality industry. Another

characteristic was that there was a good structure in place that captured in time those employees that were due for promotion, as the majority of about 68% gave positive responses comprising of 42.3% (SA), 15.5% (Agreed) and 10.3% (PA) to affirm that employees were not unnecessarily delayed when it was time for promotion.

Concerning the objective 2, the respondents agreed that Employees Performance Appraisal and Employees Performance Feedback motivated Employees' Productivity in the hotel industry. About 79% majority in table 3 comprising of 31% (SA), 27.7% (Agreed) and 20.2% (PA) affirmed positively that there was adequate employee performance feedback. Likewise, the majority of about 69% in table 3 comprising of 22.5% (SA), 33% (Agreed) and 13% (PA) affirmed positively that there was adequate Employees Performance Appraisal that allowed enough employee participation in the management style of the industry. Also, the majority of about 67% in table 4 comprising of 40.4% (SA) and 26.8% (Agreed) affirmed positively that there was adequate Employee participation in the Employees Performance Appraisal exercise that allowed enough employee participation in the management of the industry.

In line with the objective 3, the study showed that the most favoured reward package in the study area was the salary with bonuses/fringe benefits. The majority of about 79% in table 2 comprising of 41.3% (SA), 23.5% (Agreed) and 12.2% affirmed positively that there was adequate fringe benefits including bonuses that motivated employee for higher productivity in the industry. An in-depth interview with all the senior managers of the hotels revealed that the fringe benefits encompass incentives, appreciation, health benefits, bonuses and other salary packages that might vary from one hotel to another depending on whether it was a one-star hotel, 2-star, 3-star, 4-star or 5-star hotels. The in-depth interview also revealed that salary and bonus packages are the most prominent and highly favoured in the reward system packages.

The study also showed that reward system ($(\beta = .106, t = 2.843, P < .05), (r = 0.685)$), has a relative influence and significant relationship with employee productivity. Thus, in explaining objective 4, this study showed that Reward is an important factor in enhancing employees' productivity. Therefore, in tune with the objective 5, the reward system should be well harmonised and maintained to improve continuous employee productivity in the industry.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study was designed to investigate the effect of reward management on employee Productivity in the hospitality industry in Lagos state, Nigeria. The population for this study comprised of all the one hundred and three hotels registered under booking.com as hotels in Lagos state. The Yamane formula was used to arrive at 82 hotels as samples for this study. Also, the study used purposive sampling, considering the availability of the respondents to select four (4) respondents per hotel. A multistage

sampling method was used to select 328 employees. The research instruments used for data collection were questionnaire and indepth interview. Data were analysed using descriptive and regression statistics tools. The results showed the existence of a well-structured reward system in the study area, characterised by employees' recognition for jobs well done in the hotel, availability of adequate fringe benefits and bonuses for employees together with competitive salary packages and timely promotion, without delays for employees that performed well. The study further showed that most preferred reward packages include salary and bonus packages. The reward system ($\beta = .106$, $t = 2.843$, $P < .05$), ($r = 0.685$) was shown to have relative influence and significant relationship with employee's productivity. The study concluded that reward management practice is a very important factor in enhancing the productivity of employees, as evidenced by the study.

It is recommended that the Organisation should take reward management system very important for effective and efficient employees' productivity.

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